

The role of fires in the transformation of soil organic matter

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A significant part of the carbon in Northern ecosystems is concentrated in soils. Fires are one of the permanent and significant factors affecting ecosystems. The impact of fires on ecosystems is complex and can have both a positive effect on individual tree species and contribute to significant degradation of ecosystems. Together with climate, the pyrogenic factor controls the age structure and mosaic nature of the vegetation cover, its further evolution and the flows of matter and energy and soil and ecosystem carbon pools. The frequency of fires in the boreal forests of the European North of Russia varies from one or two per century to one or two per millennium. In addition, current climate changes lead to active burning of ecosystems that are weakly susceptible to fires in normal years. However, the role of fires in the formation and transformation of soil organic matter is rarely taken into account when assessing soil organic matter. The purpose of this work is to reveal the possibilities of various methods for assessing the properties of soil organic matter due to the influence of fires and to reveal the possible consequences of fire impact on the properties of SOM.

The biomass of woody vegetation and ground cover plants, litter are most exposed to pyrogenic effects. The determining factors for the compounds formed during a fire are the initial biochemical composition, temperature, and oxygen availability during the combustion process. The bioclimatic conditions of the Northern landscapes of Eurasia contribute to the prevalence of low-intensity fires in which partial combustion of biomass occur. To assess the pyrogenic impact on soil organic matter, methods are often used that allow identifying compounds and structures with an aromatic nature. Chromatographic approaches are most widely used, allowing for the isolation of polycyclic aromatic compounds (PAHs), benzene polycarboxylic acids (BPCAs) and the capabilities of nuclear magnetic resonance are widely used. It is shown that the methods used have a number of limitations and advantages. The most correct way to judge the composition of pyrogenic organic matter is to judge by the total concentration of BPCAs. The content of PAHs can mark the pyrogenic impact, the greatest indicative value is played by the concentrations of two and three-cyclic PAHs. For a number of soils, pyrogenesis is an important factor determining the aromaticity of soil organic matter, the content of PAHs and, in general, determines the pyrogenic path of transformation of organic compounds.

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